

Influence of Waveform Orthogonality and Array Geometry on Compressed Sensing Algorithms for CDMA MIMO Radar

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Abstract— Compressed Sensing (CS) has been proven as an effective technique to ease the burden due to computational loads and mitigate waveform artifacts such as sidelobes, in the case of Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) radar systems. Though orthogonal codes are a general required for the system, the question as to how the correlation properties of these sequences or the choice of array geometry contribute towards performance of CS algorithms, individually or jointly, has not been analysed. In this paper we present a study which investigates the influence of waveform orthogonality and array geometry as parameters influencing the CS algorithms reconstruction performance. The numerical simulations have been carried out for a CS-CDMA MIMO radar reconstructing a 2D range-angle (RA) target scene with multiple targets, using different code sequences in combination with different array geometries. The results present how the right combination of array configuration and transmission waveform leads to lower estimation errors and increased probability of success.

Keywords— Compressed Sensing, Range-Angle estimation, Sparse Signal Processing, BPDN, Match filter, Random Array, ULA, Probability of success.

I. INTRODUCTION

Waveform orthogonality in MIMO radar systems can be achieved by various strategies, which includes Time Division Multiplexing (TDM), Frequency Division Multiplexing (FDM), Doppler Division Multiplexing (DDM) and Code Division Multiplexing (CDM). Although TDM, FDM and DDM provide very good orthogonality, each strategy has its own limitations, TDM suffers from ambiguities in angle and Doppler domains, FDM suffers from range azimuth coupling, DDM suffers from Doppler ambiguities, in comparison CDM only produces approximate orthogonality but suffers from only high sidelobes. Since sidelobes are a result of conventional receiver processing algorithm in contrast to ambiguities which are a false replication of the target, advanced signal processing techniques such as CS can be used as an effective solution to mitigate sidelobes [2], [3].

In classical literature, CS is defined as the problem to reconstruct the coefficients of an unknown vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^N$

from a linear system of equations given by $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^M$, where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ is the so called sensing matrix, provided the condition \mathbf{x} is \mathbf{G} sparse, i.e. $\dots \mathbf{G} < \mathbf{M} \ll \mathbf{N}$, thus if \mathbf{x} has a sufficiently sparse representation and \mathbf{A} has a relatively random, \mathbf{x} can be recovered from \mathbf{y} accurately using CS algorithms such as basis pursuit (BP) and orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) [5]–[7]. The use of CS for MIMO systems, is an extension of the idea introduced by Herman and Strohmer in [4] where a sparse range-Doppler plane was successfully reconstructed using CS algorithms. In MIMO radar systems, angular parameters are an addition to the existing range and Doppler space, as a result, the new dimension bring forth possibility for the condition of sparsity to be often met [1], [5].

However, when considering the recovery guarantees by CS algorithms such as OMP and BP, the mutual coherence of the sensing matrix \mathbf{A} has a valuable role to play. The mutual coherence denoted by $\mu(\mathbf{A})$ is defined as

$$\mu(\mathbf{A}) \triangleq \max_{i \neq j} \frac{|\mathbf{a}_i^H \mathbf{a}_j|}{\|\mathbf{a}_i\| \|\mathbf{a}_j\|} \quad (1)$$

where, \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{a}_j are columns of \mathbf{A} . Lower the value $\mu(\mathbf{A})$ better is the reconstruction of \mathbf{x} . To be more precise, if $\|\mathbf{x}\|_0 < \frac{1}{2}(1 + \mu^{-1}(\mathbf{A}))$, where $\|\cdot\|_0$ denotes the l_0 norm which represents the number of non zero elements. Given the condition is met reconstruction algorithms are guaranteed to recover the optimal \mathbf{x} .

In the case of MIMO radar systems the sensing matrix is function of the system configuration, mainly array geometry and correlation properties of the transmitted waveform, as the rows correspond to the measurements received by the receiver array and columns correspond to samples of transmitted signal now augmented by the scene. The goal of this paper is to analyse and present the influence of the array geometry and transmitted waveform on $\mu(\mathbf{A})$.

The paper is organised as follows, Section II introduces the signal model and problem formulation, section III presents the CS algorithm BPDN for MIMO scene reconstruction with a simple scene reconstruction along with numerical analysis carried on different array configurations in combinations with different waveforms, to validate the scope of the research

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 860370.

question. Section IV concludes the paper with a summary of the findings.

II. SIGNAL MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. MIMO Signal Model

Consider a MIMO radar system of L transmitters and Q receivers, let the waveform $s(t)$ coded with a binary sequence c of length K given by

$$s(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} c(k) \text{rect}\left(\frac{t - kT_c}{T_c}\right) \quad (2)$$

where, k is the index for each code chip, T_c is chip duration, T_r is the total duration of the sequence given by $T_r = K * T_c$. The term $c(k)$ represents the k^{th} chip of the code sequence from a code matrix $C \in L \times K$, for a code family chosen from literature [refer some code literature]. Let the waveform radiated from the l^{th} transmitting antenna at the direction θ is given by

$$\mathbf{b}_L(t, \theta) = \mathbf{s}_l(t) \exp(jk_0 v_l \cos(\theta)) \quad (3)$$

where, $\mathbf{s}_l(t)$ is the waveform coded with the sequence corresponding to the l^{th} row of the code matrix C , the exponential term corresponds to signal model for the array response in the direction θ with v_l is position of the receiver element on the receiver array, k_0 is the wave number.

The CDM strategy follows simultaneous transmission from all L transmitters, thus each transmitters radiates a coded waveform based on the code sequence from the code matrix C given by

$$\mathbf{b}(t, \theta) = \mathbf{a}_L(\theta)^T \mathbf{s}_L(t) \quad (4)$$

where, $\mathbf{a}_L(\theta)$ is signal model representing the array configuration with L transmitters.

Let the radiated signals be incident on a scene with G targets, and be received by the Q receivers, the received signal is thus is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}_Q(t) &= \sum_{g=1}^G \beta_g \mathbf{a}_Q(\theta_g) b(t - \tau_g, \theta_g) \\ &= \sum_{g=1}^G \beta_g \mathbf{a}_Q(\theta_g) \mathbf{a}_L(\theta_g)^T \mathbf{s}_L(t - \tau_g) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Consider the signal to be sampled at a sub-Nyquist frequency, thus let M_t be the number of fast time samples, which runs from 1 to M_t , as a result we get a range value from R_0 to $R_0 + r_{nr} \Delta r$ where r_{nr} corresponds to each range bin with respect to an echo received from the k^{th} bit of the code. Thus relation of the range bin r_{nr} , code length K and fast time is $r_{nr} = 1 - K \dots M_t - 1$. As a result the total number of range bins is $N_r = M_t + K - 1$. Let the angular grid be represented by equally spaced N_u points corresponding to the radar bore-sight, thus $u_{nu} = \cos(nu)$, represents the direction cosine for a point nu on the angular grid. Thus the discretized version of the received signal for a single point

target (neglecting any contributing terms to slow time) at each q^{th} receiver and m_t instance is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{s}(m_t, q, nr, nu) &= \beta \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \exp\{jk_0(u_{nu}(p_q + v_l))\} \\ &\quad \times C(l, k) \delta(k - (m_t - nr)) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where, nr, nu are indexes corresponding to the range and angle bin occupied by the target with complex amplitude β .

As the focus of this study is to investigate the parameters influencing the estimation of β from equation (6) when using CS algorithms, we now consider representing the MIMO signal model in the compressed sensing frame work.

B. 2D-CS MIMO Model

Consider the total number of unknowns as $N = N_r \times N_u$ the total number of measurements as $M = M_t \times Q$, therefore each row index is given by $n = nr + (nu - 1)N_r$ and each column index is given by $m = m_t + (q - 1)M_t$, each code index for the vectorized code matrix C is given by $c = k + (l - 1)K$. The sensing matrix for the MIMO radar can be considered as a dictionary of all possible range and angular values which would be observed by the Q receivers from code sequences of length K radiated from L transmitted, given by $A \in M \times N$. The coefficients of the sensing matrix is given by

$$\begin{aligned} a_{mn} &= \sum_c \exp\{jk_0(u_{nu}(n)(p_q(m) + v_l(c)))\} \\ &\quad \times C(L(c), K(c)) \delta(K(c) - (m_t(m) - nr(n))) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Thus for each receiver and we have a matrix \mathbf{A}_{Q, N_u} with coefficients as given in equation (7), which are stacked together to form a the final sensing matrix \mathbf{A} , which can be visualized as below.

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{1,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{A}_{1,N_u} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{A}_{Q,1} & \cdots & \mathbf{A}_{Q,N_u} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The complex amplitude corresponding to targets present in the scene imaged by N_r range bins and N_u directions cosines can be represent as a vector of unknowns $\mathbf{x} \in N \times 1$, the received measurements from the Q receivers can be represented as vector $\mathbf{y} \in M \times 1$. Thus the linear relationship of the measurements to the scene of unknown complex amplitudes for a noiseless case can be given by

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{y} is dense, \mathbf{A} is a fat matrix and \mathbf{x} is a sparse vector where the non-zero indexes are occupied by the complex amplitude β_g corresponding to the G targets. Provided the condition $G < M \ll N$ is satisfied, CS algorithms to estimate β , as the indexes of the $N \times 1$ unknowns is $n = nr + (nu - 1)N_r$, who's rows are orthonormal to the columns of \mathbf{A} , thus it is possible to estimate nr and nu from \mathbf{x} .

C. Problem Formulation

Since sparsity of the scene is generally not a limitation in MIMO radar case, the only option which provides the opportunity to improve the reconstruction efficiency of CS algorithms is $\mu(\mathbf{A})$. As seen in (7) the coefficients of the sensing matrix are a function of the transmitted code sequences and Tx/Rx element positions, hence it is safe to say the coherence of the sensing matrix $\mu(\mathbf{A})$ is dependent on parameters $v_l, p_q, C(L, K)$. There have been many studies which focus on designing algorithms which are concentrated directly on coherence minimisation [refer lit of coherence minimisation], however this study focuses on validating these approaches that antenna positions and waveform correlation are indeed the influencing factors or the parameters which are optimised in coherence minimisation algorithms, by the means of numerical simulations.

III. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

A. CS Reconstruction

Fig. 1. Comparison of a target scene reconstructed using FFT and the same performed using CS algorithm BPDN

In order to improve the reconstruction of a CS algorithm the sensing matrix \mathbf{A} needs to be incoherent, "Lower the coherence better is the reconstruction" [refer profender paper].

In the following sections we consider array geometry and waveform correlation as parameters impacting coherence and influencing reconstruction.

B. Array Configurations

The general signal model for a Tx/Rx array is given by

$$a(\theta) = \exp\{jk_0(x_i \cos(\theta))\} \quad (10)$$

where, x_i corresponds to the position of the array elements and θ the direction of scan in case of the Tx array and direction of arrival in case of the Rx array.

The information of the array positions (spacing between the array elements), directly relates to statistical manifold of the Fisher information matrix of the MIMO signal model [refer Sparse-signal processing on information-based range grid]. Hence the study of how regularly spaced points in case of an Uniform Linear Array (ULA), points based on numerical combinations such as the Coprime array and points chosen at random from a larger array, known in literature as "Thinned array" or termed here as Random array, influence the coherence of the sensing matrix \mathbf{A} , and finally lead to improvement in reconstruction capability of a CS algorithm, is worthy of investigation.

C. Waveform Correlation

In the scope of this study we do not focus on the design of the sequence but merely the use of the available sequence from literature. We consider a sequence with random phase and the Binary sequence with low ISL from [9] which have good correlation properties and two sequences of with low correlation. The comparison of the estimation error when using a sequence of good correlation against that of poor correlation are analysed in the numerical analysis.

D. Numerical Results

- Number of transmitting elements $L = 3$.
- Number of receiving elements $Q = 4$.
- Number of Monte Carlo iterations = 300.
- Length of the transmitted sequence $K = 64$.
- Number of direction cosine $N_u = 20$.
- Number of range-bins $N_r = 157$.
- Antenna Configuration is Random thinned array.
- Transmitted beampattern is Omnidirectional.

In figure 2 we present the simulation results showing the reconstruction error of the BPDN algorithm, from the three candidate arrays. A code sequence of random phase given by $\exp(j2\pi\phi_{l,k})$ are simultaneously transmitted and received on from a scene consisting of multiple targets of different signal strengths.

It is clearly seen that the Random array produces the least minimum mean square error (mmse) in comparison to the other candidates, this is, as a result of irregularly spaced positions which makes the columns of a \mathbf{A} created using a random array more further apart and the later two, thereby reducing coherence and improving CS reconstruction performance.

Fig. 2.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this draft paper, a proof of concept, validating the dependence of array geometry and waveform correlation on the performance of the CS algorithm BPDN has been presented.

The final version will extend the study towards other CS algorithms such as OMP and additional dimensions such as range-doppler.

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